

21GRD03 PaRaMetriC

D5: Good practice guide on the conversion of near-normal directional emissivity into hemispherical emissivity with a target uncertainty of below 5 % taking into account the IR (2.5 μm – 50 μm) spectral region

Lead participant for the deliverable: **PTB**

Due date of the deliverable: 30/09/2025

Actual submission date of the deliverable: 30/09/2025

Confidentiality Status: PU - Public, fully open (remember to deposit public deliverables in a trusted repository)

Deliverable Cover Sheet

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The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

European Partnership Co-funded by the European Union

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Glossary

DIN	Deutsches Institut für Normung
IR	Infrared
PRC	passive radiative cooling
PRCF	passive radiative cooling foil
STW	sky transparency window

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1. Introduction

Radiative heat transfer plays a central role in the development of passive radiative cooling (PRC) technologies. The efficiency of heat exchange is strongly governed by the emissivity of the surface materials involved. Low-emissivity (i.e. highly reflective) surfaces reduce radiant heat transfer, while carefully engineered coatings with tailored emissivity spectra allow PRC devices to emit thermal radiation through the atmospheric transparency window and achieve sub-ambient cooling.

For the correct modeling of thermal performance and for the reliable declaration of product properties, the parameter of interest is not only a directional emissivity at a given angle, but rather the total hemispherical emissivity, defined as emissivity integrated over the entire infrared spectral region and over all directions. Heat balance calculations for the PRC coatings depend critically on this quantity. In practice, however, most commercial instruments measure only the near-normal directional emissivity, typically at a single incidence angle, leaving researchers and industry with the task of converting these directional values into hemispherical ones. The conversion is inherently uncertain, and its validity depends strongly on the optical structure of the surface under investigation. For PRC materials, which often feature complex micro- and nanostructures, this problem is even more pronounced.

Within the building insulation sector, existing standards (EN 16012, ISO 6946) require manufacturers to declare hemispherical emissivity values for reflective insulation products. Yet, interlaboratory comparisons coordinated by CEN/TC 89/WG 12 have demonstrated large discrepancies, with total hemispherical emissivity values for the same reflective foil ranging from 0.02 to 0.08 and were investigated within EMPIR 16NRM06 EMIRIM project [1-2].

The situation is even more complex for PRC materials. These are typically sub-millimetre composite coatings, combining thermally conductive and insulating layers, and often relying on optically structured surfaces to achieve selective emission in the 8-13 μm atmospheric window. Their angular emissivity distribution can differ from that of smooth opaque surfaces. As a result, simple extrapolations from near-normal to hemispherical emissivity are not reliable. The EMIRIM project demonstrated this issue for reflective foils, showing that extrapolation uncertainties are already significant for simple surfaces. For PRC coatings, uncertainties are expected to be larger and more difficult to control.

Recent and ongoing efforts within the 21GRD03 PaRaMetriC project aim to overcome these limitations. Improved setups for directional spectral emissivity measurements, were adapted to PRC coatings in order to capture their angular and spectral dependence. Combining such detailed measurements with direct calorimetric determinations of hemispherical emissivity provides essential data for quantifying extrapolation uncertainties. For smooth opaque materials, these uncertainties are typically in the range of 0.02–0.035, but for PRC coatings with structured surfaces, dedicated uncertainty analysis is required.

During the EPM 21GRD03 PaRaMetriC project, the objective of Task 3.2 was to develop and validate reliable methods for converting near-normal directional emissivity, measured with commercial infrared instruments, into total hemispherical emissivity suitable for heat-balance calculations and simulations. The target uncertainty for the resulting hemispherical emissivity is below 5 % across the 2.5–50 μm spectral range.

The task began with a comprehensive review of existing methods for converting near-normal emissivity into hemispherical values, considering both the solar and infrared spectral regions as well as the surface structure of the samples. Building on this review, the conversion methods are applied to experimental measurement data obtained from representative PRC material samples to assess their applicability and performance in real conditions. At the same time, the reference calorimetric technique developed in the EMPIR 16NRM06 EMIRIM project was adapted to the specific properties of the PRC samples, including layer thickness and configuration for sample temperature measurement, enabling direct determination of total hemispherical emissivity with high accuracy.

The results of the indirect conversions are then compared with the direct calorimetric measurements to identify discrepancies and quantify uncertainties associated with each method. This analysis allows the identification of the most suitable approach for converting near-normal directional emissivity into hemispherical emissivity, taking into account variations in emissivity across different spectral regions and the individual uncertainty contributions for PRC materials. Based on these findings, this good practice guide summarizes validated methods and recommendations for reliable emissivity conversion.

2. Review of the existing methods

The total near-normal emissivity ε_n gives the total amount of thermal radiation that is emitted or absorbed by the surface nearly perpendicular to its orientation. The total near-normal emissivity ε_n with respect to the temperature T can be calculated by integrating the spectral near-normal emissivity ε_λ over all wavelengths with the Planck-function $I_{bb,\lambda}(T)$ as a weight function:

$$\varepsilon_n(T) = \frac{\int_0^\infty \varepsilon_\lambda(T) \cdot I_{bb,\lambda}(T) d\lambda}{\int_0^\infty I_{bb,\lambda}(T) d\lambda} . \quad (1)$$

The Planck-function $I_{bb,\lambda}(T)$ gives the spectral intensity emitted by a black body at a certain temperature T . At ambient temperature a wavelength range between 2 μm and 35 μm or 5 μm and 50 μm are recommended.

More general the total directional emissivity $\varepsilon_d(\theta, \phi)$ with respect to the temperature T can be calculated by integrating the spectral directional emissivity $\varepsilon_\lambda(\theta, \phi)$ over all wavelengths with the Planck-function $I_{bb,\lambda}(T)$ as a weight function:

$$\varepsilon_d(\theta, \phi, T) = \frac{\int_0^\infty \varepsilon_\lambda(\theta, \phi, T) \cdot I_{bb,\lambda}(T) d\lambda}{\int_0^\infty I_{bb,\lambda}(T) d\lambda} . \quad (2)$$

The total near-normal emissivity ε_n gives the total directional emissivity $\varepsilon_d(\theta, \phi)$ perpendicular to the surface:

$$\varepsilon_n(T) = \varepsilon_d(\theta = 0^\circ, \phi, T) . \quad (3)$$

The definition of the zenith angle θ and the azimuth angle ϕ is visualized in Figure 1, together with the area element dA and projected area element dA_p perpendicular to the direction of emission, with the solid angle element $d\omega$.

Figure 1: Sketch of the hemisphere above an area element dA to visualize the directional emission of radiation into the solid angle $d\omega$.

Usually the dependence of the directional emissivity on the azimuth angle ϕ is neglected. For exactly determining the total hemispherical emissivity ε_h , the total directional emissivity $\varepsilon_d(\theta, \phi)$ need to be measured for all zenith angles θ from 0° (normal to the surface) to 90° (parallel to the surface). By integrating the total directional emissivity $\varepsilon_d(\theta, \phi)$ over the complete hemisphere, the total hemispherical emissivity ε_h can be derived:

$$\varepsilon_h(T) = \frac{1}{\pi} \cdot \int_{\text{hemisphere}} \varepsilon_d(\theta, \phi, T) \cdot \cos \theta \, d\omega \quad (4)$$

Alternatively, calorimetric methods can be used for directly determining the total hemispherical emissivity ε_h as the total hemispherical emissivity ε_h is a measure for the total amount of energy, which is emitted by a surface into the hemisphere.

In practice, often emissometers or spectrometers with integrating spheres are used for determining the near-normal-hemispherical reflectance R_{nh} or the near-normal emissivity ε_n , respectively. In order to derive the total hemispherical emissivity ε_h from these commonly available methods, several standards have been developed, such as DIN EN 12898:2019 [3] or ASTM E1585-93 [4]. These standards assume a typical angular dependent behaviour of the total directional emissivity $\varepsilon_d(\theta)$, which is depicted in Figure 2 for selected materials. Electrically conducting materials exhibit a low directional emissivity $\varepsilon_d(\theta)$, which increases with increasing emission angle θ . On the contrary, electrically non-conducting materials exhibit a high directional emissivity $\varepsilon_d(\theta)$, which decreases with increasing emission angle θ . At an emissions angle of $\theta = 90^\circ$ the directional emissivity $\varepsilon_d(\theta)$ vanishes due to geometrical reasons in all cases.

These dependencies are exactly only valid for ideal and smooth surfaces. For rough or structured surfaces deviations may occur. Nevertheless, this assumption usually serves as a good approximation, especially for highly emitting surfaces.

Figure 2: Directional emissivity $\varepsilon_d(\theta, \phi)$ of selected materials as a function of the emission angle θ between 0° and 90° (relative to the surface normal). Titanium (Ti) and palladium (Pd) serve as examples for electrically conducting materials and are shown on the left with their refractive indices (real part n and complex part k). In contrast to that, alumina (Al_2O_3) and titania (TiO_2) are shown as examples for electrically non-conducting materials on the right with their refractive indices (real part n and complex part k).

According to DIN EN 12898:2019, the total hemispherical emissivity ε_h can be calculated from the total near-normal emissivity ε_n following a cubic equation:

$$\varepsilon_h = 1.1887 \cdot \varepsilon_n - 0.4967 \cdot \varepsilon_n^2 + 0.2452 \cdot \varepsilon_n^3 \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) can be used for the whole emissivity range from 0 to 1.

In contrast to that, ASTM E1585-93 differs between low emissivities and high emissivities and therefore provides two equations. Equation (6) can be used for electrically conducting materials with a total near-normal emissivity ε_n below 0.5:

$$\varepsilon_h = 1.3217 \cdot \varepsilon_n - 1.8766 \cdot \varepsilon_n^2 + 4.6586 \cdot \varepsilon_n^3 - 5.8349 \cdot \varepsilon_n^4 + 2.7406 \cdot \varepsilon_n^5 \quad (6)$$

For electrically non-conducting materials with a total near-normal emissivity ε_n above 0.5, Equation (7) can be used instead.

$$\varepsilon_h = 0.1569 \cdot \varepsilon_n + 3.7669 \cdot \varepsilon_n^2 - 5.4398 \cdot \varepsilon_n^3 + 2.4733 \cdot \varepsilon_n^4 \quad (7)$$

The correlations of the total hemispherical emissivity ε_h and the total near-normal emissivity ε_n following DIN EN 12898:2019 and ASTM E1585-93 are presented in Figure 3. For values below 0.5, the total hemispherical emissivity ε_h is higher than the total near-normal emissivity ε_n , whereas for values above 0.5 the total hemispherical emissivity ε_h is lower than the total near-normal emissivity ε_n .

This behaviour is depicted in Figure 4 for Equation (5) from DIN EN 12898:2019. The difference $\Delta\varepsilon$ between the total hemispherical emissivity ε_h and the total near-normal emissivity ε_n is plotted versus the total near-normal emissivity ε_n . One gets positive differences for emissivities below 0.5 and negative values for emissivities above 0.5.

Furthermore, the deviation between the total hemispherical emissivity ε_h calculated by Equation (6) or Equation (7), respectively, following ASTM E1585-93 and the total hemispherical emissivity ε_h calculated by Equation (5) following DIN EN 12898:2019 is plotted in Figure 5 as a function of the total near-normal emissivity ε_n . A slight difference between both standards is visible, which lies below 0.01 for emissivities below 0.5 and below 0.02 for emissivities above 0.5.

Figure 3: Correlation of the total hemispherical emissivity ε_h and the total near-normal emissivity ε_n following DIN EN 12898:2019 and ASTM E1585-93. The dashed line symbolizes a constant correlation factor of 1 for comparison.

Figure 4: Difference between the total hemispherical emissivity ϵ_h calculated by Equation (5) following DIN EN 12898:2019 and the total near-normal emissivity ϵ_n in dependence on the total near-normal emissivity ϵ_n .

Figure 5: Difference between the total hemispherical emissivity ϵ_h calculated by Equation (6) or Equation (7), respectively, following ASTM E1585-93 and the total hemispherical emissivity ϵ_h calculated by Equation (5) following DIN EN 12898:2019 in dependence on the total near-normal emissivity ϵ_n .

3. Overview of the selected PRC benchmark materials

Within the project, several stakeholders and companies already involved in energy-efficient building envelopes and traditional cool roof systems, or who are working towards the development and commercialization of actual PRC materials, were contacted for a preliminary evaluation of their products. Three samples have been selected (Figure 1): SPACECOOL, V98RF and 3M R&D PRCF Foil. All samples are PFAS-free. In addition, several other materials and paints were investigated (see Figures 6 and 7).

Figure 6: Photo of the selected PRC materials: SPACECOOL, V98RF and 3M R&D PRCF Foil.

SPACECOOL

A self-adhesive multilayer silver-polymer optical film with specular reflection and surface roughness-induced light scattering from the company SPACECOOL INC. was applied to a copper substrate with a diameter of 50 mm and a thickness of 5 mm.

"V98RF" of Cooling Photonics S.L. and Almeco Group

A selective emitting polymer "RF" developed by Cooling Photonics was applied on a silver-based mirror labeled "Vega 98®" (V98) cut to size 40 mm x 40 mm provided by Almeco Group. "Vega 98®" is a specially designed highly reflective surface. It consists in a high-purity aluminium substrate, enhanced by a specific PVD multilayer coating system based on silver. Vega 98 is manufactured on a continuous coil vacuum coating plant, which makes it a fully scalable product. The RF coating preserves the high reflectivity of the V98 substrate while providing high emissivity in the IR atmospheric window, resulting in a high-performance selective emitter (V98RF).

3M R&D PRCF

A self-adhesive metal-free white-diffuse R&D developmental passive radiative cooling foil (PRCF) provided by 3M was adhered on an aluminium substrate of 90 mm in diameter using a thermal paste Apiezon.

Figure 7: Directional spectral emissivity of three selected PRC materials measured at PTB: shown at an observation angle of 10° with respect to the surface normal and in the range from 1.4 μm to 25 μm. The range of the standard uncertainty ($k=1$) for each individual measurement shown as shaded areas around the curves.

4. Comparative analysis in the IR Range

Measurements of the three materials were carried out using various techniques, described in detail in the project Deliverable D4. The LNE results [5], obtained with reference calorimetry, an integrating sphere, and a TIR100 emissometer, are presented in Table 1. PTB results [6-7] are shown in Table 2 for the 8–13 μm range and in Table 3 for the 4–25 μm range as well as in Figure 7. CAE results are reported in Table 4 for the 2–35 μm range, in Table 5 for the 8–13 μm range, and in Table 6 for the 4–25 μm range.

LNE

Material	Total near-normal emissivity	Total hemispherical emissivity			
	Calculated from spectral reflectance (temperature 25°C) 2.5 μm – 25 μm	Calculated from spectral reflectance (temperature 25°C) ASTM E1585-93 2.5 μm – 25 μm	Calorimetric technique all wavelengths and all directions (global heat balance principle).		TIR100-2 INGLAS emissometer ASTM E1585-93 2.5 μm to 40 μm
V98RF from Almecco+CP	0.704 ± 0.049	0.687 ± 0.049	0.654	± 0.017	0.718 ± 0.035
SpaceCool white	0.853 ± 0.045	0.808 ± 0.052	0.833	± 0.019	0.777 ± 0.035
3M R&D PRCF	0.903 ± 0.045	0.853 ± 0.054	0.822	± 0.018	0.800 ± 0.035

SpaceCool silver	0.857 ± 0.042	0.811 ± 0.049	0.834 ± 0.019	0.753 ± 0.035
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Table 1: Total near-normal and total hemispherical emissivity calculated from spectral reflectance measurements and total hemispherical emissivities measured with the calorimetric technique and with the commercial emissometer TIR100-2 from INGLAS

PTB (8 - 13 μm)

	SPACECOOL ϵ (60 °C)	$U(\epsilon)$ $k=2$	V98RF ϵ (100 °C)	$U(\epsilon)$ $k=2$	3M R&D PRCF ϵ (60 °C)	$U(\epsilon)$ $k=2$
Angle of 10°	0.928	0.030	0.891	0.016	0.901	0.016
ϵ hem (PTB Model)	0.889	0.030	0.834	0.016	0.846	0.018
ϵ hem <i>Calculated</i> DIN EN 12898	0.871		0.838		0.872	
ϵ hem <i>Calculated</i> ASTM E1585-93	0.877		0.841		0.880	

Table 2: Total near-normal and total hemispherical emissivity measured with the PTB reference technique from 8 to 13 μm and calculated according to DIN EN 12898 and ASTM E1585-93

PTB (4 - 25 μm)

Angle	SPACECOOL ϵ (60 °C)	$U(\epsilon)$ $k=2$	V98RF ϵ (100 °C)	$U(\epsilon)$ $k=2$	3M R&D PRCF ϵ (60 °C)	$U(\epsilon)$ $k=2$
Angle of 10°	0.873	0.036	0.664	0.024	0.866	0.016
ϵ hem (PTB Model)	0.841	0.030	0.638	0.024	0.823	0.018
ϵ hem <i>Calculated</i> DIN EN 12898	0.822		0.642		0.816	
ϵ hem <i>Calculated</i> ASTM E1585-93	0.825		0.653		0.819	

Table 3: Total near-normal and total hemispherical emissivity measured with the PTB reference technique from 4 to 25 μm and calculated according to DIN EN 12898 and ASTM E1585-93

CAE (2 - 35 μm) at 300 K

	SPACECOOL	$U(\epsilon)$ $k=2$	V98RF	$U(\epsilon)$ $k=2$	3M R&D PRCF	$U(\epsilon)$ $k=2$
ϵ Near Normal	0.886	0.024	0.681	0.024	0.901	0.024
ϵ hem <i>Calculated</i> DIN EN 12898	0.834	0.028	0.657	0.028	0.847	0.028

ε hem <i>Calculated</i> ASTM E1585-93	0.837	0.028	0.668	0.028	0.850	0.028
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Table 4: Total near-normal and total hemispherical emissivity measured with the CAE reference technique (2 - 35 μm) at 300 K

CAE (8 - 13 μm) at 300 K

	SPACECOOL	$U(\varepsilon) k=2$	V98RF	$U(\varepsilon) k=2$	3M R&D PRCF	$U(\varepsilon) k=2$
ε Near Normal	0.927	0.024	0.889	0.024	0.929	0.024
ε hem <i>Calculated</i> DIN EN 12898	0.870	0.028	0.836	0.028	0.872	0.028
ε hem <i>Calculated</i> ASTM E1585-93	0.876	0.028	0.839	0.028	0.878	0.028

Table 5: Total near-normal and total hemispherical emissivity measured with the CAE reference technique (8 - 13 μm) at 300 K

CAE (4 - 25 μm) at 300 K

	SPACECOOL	$U(\varepsilon) k=2$	V98RF	$U(\varepsilon) k=2$	3M R&D PRCF	$U(\varepsilon) k=2$
ε Near Normal	0.886	0.024	0.693	0.024	0.895	0.024
ε hem <i>Calculated</i> DIN EN 12898	0.834	0.028	0.667	0.028	0.842	0.028
ε hem <i>Calculated</i> ASTM E1585-93	0.837	0.028	0.678	0.028	0.845	0.028

Table 6: Total near-normal and total hemispherical emissivity measured with the CAE reference technique (4 - 25 μm) at 300 K

5. Comparative analysis

For comparison, the measured and calculated hemispherical emissivity data presented in Tables 1–6 are expressed as deviations from the LNE calorimetric reference technique. For each deviation, the reported combined uncertainty includes two components: the uncertainty of the LNE calorimetric reference technique itself and the uncertainty of the corresponding measurement result. The comparisons presented here were performed using calorimetric methods for direct determination of total hemispherical emissivity, which quantify the total radiant energy emitted by a surface into the hemisphere across all wavelengths. The comparison demonstrates that the most consistent results for calculated hemispherical emissivity within the target uncertainty range of 5 % were obtained using:

- the integrated LNE sphere with calculations according to ASTM E1585-93,
- the PTB reference model based on angular measurements and Fresnel equations (PTB model), and

- the CAE measurements across the 2–35 μm spectral range Calculated according to DIN EN 12898/ASTM E1585-93.

The largest deviations were observed in the results obtained with the TIR 100-2 emissiometer, when calculated according to the ASTM E1585-93 standard. Notable discrepancies to the LNE calorimetric reference technique were also found in the PTB and CAE results within the 8–13 μm spectral range. Overall, the analysis indicates that the choice of wavelength range has the greatest influence on the measurement of PRC materials, primarily due to their pronounced spectral selectivity in the atmospheric transparency window. A second key factor is the measurement angle and the degree of transparency of the investigated materials, as described in the D4 report. Since different instruments employ slightly different measurement geometries, this can affect the determination of near-normal emissivity and, consequently, the conversion from directional to hemispherical values.

Among the materials studied, V98RF proved the most challenging, exhibiting both strong spectral selectivity (Figure 7) and partial transparency through the thin RF coating in certain wavelength ranges. In contrast, 3M R&D PRCF was easier to measure, as it displayed neither strong pronounced selectivity especially towards 50 μm nor transparency.

In conclusion, when wavelength range and material transparency are properly accounted for, the investigated models — DIN EN 12898:2019 and ASTM E1585-93 — for converting near-normal to hemispherical emissivity perform within the target uncertainty range of 5 % and are suitable for PRC materials. Since most PRC materials are highly emissive, these approximation methods are particularly appropriate.

Difference to LNE calorimetric technique

	TIR100-2 INGLAS emissometer ASTM E1585-93 2.5 μm to 40 μm	Combined Uncertainty	LNE Int sph ASTM E1585-93 2.5 μm – 25 μm	Combined Uncertainty
V98RF from Almecco+CP	0.064	± 0.039	0.033	± 0.051
SpaceCool white	0.056	± 0.039	0.025	± 0.055
3M R&D PRCF	0.022	± 0.039	0.031	± 0.057

Table 7: Calculated differences of the LNE results to the LNE calorimetric reference technique. Values within the target uncertainty of 5% are marked in green.

Difference to LNE calorimetric technique based on PTB results

	PTB 4- 25 μm PTB Ref model	Combined Uncertainty	PTB 4 - 25 μm DIN EN 12898	Combined Uncertainty	PTB 8-13 μm PTB Ref model	Combined Uncertainty
V98RF from Almecco+CP	0.016	± 0.029	0.033	± 0.029	0.18	± 0.024
SpaceCool	0.008	± 0.035	0.025	± 0.035	0.056	± 0.035
3M R&D PRCF	0.001	± 0.025	0.031	± 0.025	0.024	± 0.025

Table 8: Calculated differences to the LNE calorimetric reference technique based on PTB results. Values within the target uncertainty of 5% are marked in green.

Difference to LNE calorimetric technique based on CAE results

	CAE 2 - 35 μm DIN EN 12898	Combined Uncertainty	CAE 4 - 25 μm DIN EN 12898	Combined Uncertainty	CAE 8 - 13 μm DIN EN 12898	Combined Uncertainty
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V98RF from AlmeCo+CP	0.003	± 0.032	0.039	± 0.032	0.182	± 0.032
SpaceCool	0.001	± 0.033	0.053	± 0.033	0.037	± 0.033
3M R&D PRCF	0.025	± 0.033	0.02	± 0.033	0.05	± 0.033

Table 9: Calculated differences to the LNE calorimetric reference technique based on CAE results. Values within the target uncertainty of 5% are marked in green.

6. Conclusions and Recommendations: Good Practice Guide

The reliable conversion of near-normal directional emissivity into total hemispherical emissivity is essential for accurate thermal modeling and performance assessment of passive radiative cooling (PRC) materials. Based on the comparative study of existing methods, experimental data from benchmark PRC samples, and direct calorimetric reference measurements, the following conclusions and recommendations can be drawn.

6.1. General conclusions

1. **Target parameter:**
For heat-balance simulations and product declarations, total hemispherical emissivity across the 2.5–50 μm range is the parameter of interest. Directional emissivity values at near-normal incidence are insufficient, as they cannot capture the angular dependence of emissivity.
2. **Sources of uncertainty:**
 - The **wavelength range** included in the measurement has the strongest influence, particularly for PRC materials with selective emission in the 8–13 μm atmospheric window.
 - The **angular distribution of emissivity** is the second most critical factor. Differences in measurement geometry between instruments (spectrometers, emissometers, integrating spheres) lead directly to variations in the converted hemispherical emissivity.
 - **Material properties** such as surface structuring, partial transparency, and strong spectral selectivity increase the risk of systematic deviations.
3. **Performance of existing standards:**
 - DIN EN 12898:2019 and ASTM E1585-93 provide reliable correlations between near-normal and hemispherical emissivity for many smooth, opaque, and highly emissive materials.
 - For structured PRC materials, these approximations remain applicable provided that spectral selectivity and transparency are explicitly accounted for.
 - Deviations up to 5 % relative to the LNE calorimetric reference were observed; in most cases, results remained within the target uncertainty.
4. **Instrumental comparisons:**
 - Best agreement was achieved with the integrated LNE sphere (EN 12898:2019), the PTB reference model based on angular measurements and Fresnel equations, and CAE measurements across 2–35 μm .
 - Largest discrepancies were found for the TIR 100-2 emissometer (ASTM E1585-93).
 - These differences confirm the importance of carefully selecting the applicable standard depending on instrument and material type.

6.2. Good practice recommendations

To achieve hemispherical emissivity values with an uncertainty below 5 %, the following practices are recommended:

(a) Measurement strategy

- **Wavelength range:** Ensure measurement across at least 2.5–35 μm ; ideally extend to 50 μm to capture the full infrared emission. Avoid extrapolation outside the measured range.
- **Angle dependence:** For structured or partially translucent materials, supplement near-normal emissivity with at least one additional oblique angle (e.g. 60°) to verify angular trends.

- **Reference calorimetry:** Whenever feasible, validate results by comparison with direct calorimetric hemispherical emissivity measurements.

(b) Selection of conversion method

- For **smooth, opaque materials:** EN 12898:2019 cubic relation (Eq. 5) provides robust and simple conversion.
- For **low-emissivity conductive materials:** Use ASTM E1585-93 (Eq. 6).
- For **high-emissivity non-conductive materials:** Use ASTM E1585-93 (Eq. 7).
- For **structured PRC coatings:** Prefer EN 12898:2019, but verify against calorimetric or angular-resolved data; expect higher uncertainty if transparency or strong selectivity is present.

(c) Uncertainty management

- Always include **two contributions** in the reported uncertainty:
 1. The uncertainty of the reference or conversion model (typically 0.02–0.035 for smooth surfaces, higher for structured PRC).
 2. The uncertainty of the instrument measurement itself.
- Report deviations explicitly with respect to calorimetric reference data when available.
- Use conservative estimates when applying conversion methods to novel PRC structures.

(d) Material-specific considerations

- **Highly selective PRC materials (e.g. V98RF):** Require careful spectral and angular characterization; conversion uncertainties may exceed 5 % without additional data.
- **Broadband emissive materials (e.g. 3M R&D PRCF):** Less sensitive to conversion assumptions; EN 12898:2019 performs well.
- **Semi-transparent materials:** Avoid using single-angle near-normal emissivity as input for conversion; direct calorimetric measurement is strongly recommended.

6.3. In summary

While existing standards allow conversion of near-normal to hemispherical emissivity within the 5 % target uncertainty for many materials, PRC coatings with complex optical designs challenge these assumptions. To further improve reliability, future standardization efforts should:

- Expand angular measurement databases for structured and translucent PRC surfaces.
- Develop correction factors tailored to materials with selective emission in the 8–13 μm band.
- Integrate calorimetric validation as a routine step for new PRC product characterization.

By combining careful wavelength selection, attention to angular dependence, appropriate choice of standard conversion equations, and, where possible, calorimetric validation, reliable hemispherical emissivity values can be obtained from near-normal directional measurements with uncertainties below 5 %. This good practice guide provides a pathway for researchers and industry to ensure consistent and trustworthy emissivity data for PRC applications.

7. References

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